

Quantum Dynamical Probability Wave Part II (High Energy Limit)

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In part I we argued that classical mechanics divides a one dimensional line into equally spaced dx regions. These are small, but not zero because classical spatial density is $C1 dt = C1 dx/ v(x)$ where $v(x)$ is velocity which is assumed to be constant within dx to first order. In terms of probability, if a particle is within a certain dx , it is not in the adjacent ones i.e a probability distribution reaches zero at the endpoints of dx . We argued that for a constant velocity classical density is $P(x)=\text{constant}$ and so one must keep two spatial probability distributions (in two dimensions or separated by i) such that the modulus is 1. This makes the two ideas compatible.

This idea seems to apply to quantum mechanics with the stipulation that dx is linked to $1/p$. Thus one has $\exp(ipx)$ as a dynamical probability as discussed in Part I. In this note we wish to consider this in more detail together with the Schrodinger equation. In particular we focus on the high energy limit. We argue that $\exp(ipx)$ should hold for a small dx region classically which may include several wavelengths proportional to $1/p$. Thus there is still the idea of the distribution and its shift as two dimensions, but we argue that the time-independent Schrodinger equation may be an approximation as it considers $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$ when creating $Wn(x)$ and it is not clear that such interference holds in a very high n limit.

$\exp(ipx)$ and Classical Physics

The arguments for $\exp(ipx)$ seem to be surprisingly classical. As argued in Part 1 one may consider the free particle classical action $A = -m_0 t \sqrt{1-vv}$ (relativistic) or $A = .5m_0 t v^2$ (nonrelativistic) and write $v=x/t$. Treating x and t as independent yields:

$$d/dx \text{ partial } A = p \text{ and } d/dt \text{ partial } A = -E \text{ or } A = -Et + px \text{ ((1))}$$

Creating an eigenvalue equation yields $-id/dx \text{ partial } \exp(iA) = p \exp(iA)$ and $id/dt \text{ partial } \exp(iA) = E \exp(iA)$ ((2))

Thus $\exp(ipx)$ the free particle wavefunction appears directly from classical arguments and so should apply in a high energy quantum limit.

Alternatively, as argued in Part 1, one may note that classical mechanics considers equally spaced small, but not zero, dx regions. The classical spatial density is $C1 dt = C1 dx/v(x)$ where $v(x)$ is the velocity. To first order $v(x)$ is a constant within dx . As a result, in order to resolve a particle within dx the probability density should be zero at the endpoints of dx . This contradicts $C1dx/ v(x)$ for a $v(x)=\text{a constant}$. As a result, it was suggested in Part I that one needs two shifted probability distributions (both which resolve dx units) kept in two dimensions such that their modulus is 1. This points to ((2)) i.e. $\exp(ipx)$. An interesting point is that there is a characteristic length $2\pi/p$ for each p which defines a dx length. It differs for different p and indicates that a particle is somewhere within this length although it still has momentum p everywhere.

$\cos(px)$ has positive and negative regions which show probability change in a sense like a classical wave.. $\sin(px)$ also has these regions. It may be noted, however, that it is the modulus which yields density. For a particle in a box with infinite potential walls a solution of $\sin(px)$ yields a density of $\sin(px)\sin(px)$ i.e. the negative and positive regions both become positive. Nevertheless the positive and negative regions of $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ play a role in interference.

Interference

For a free particle $\exp(ipx)$ shows that there is a characteristic length $2\pi\hbar/p$ and also indicates dynamics, but p and $p^2/2m$ are constants at each x . As a result, one may wonder what is the importance of $\exp(ipx)$. Consider, however, a particle in a box with infinite potential walls at $x=0$ and $x=L$. A solution of $\sin(pave x)$ where $pave = \hbar k$ ($n=1,2,3\dots$) consists of $\exp(ipave x)$ and $\exp(-ipave x)$. One might wonder why these should appear together. We argue that if a particle with $pave$ is within the wavelength with half the wavelength equaling L for the ground state there is uncertainty of this length. There is no reason the particle may have not already bounced off the wall. Thus for low lying states one needs to keep both $pave$ and $-pave$, something that would not be done in classical physics where dx is very small and the particle is either moving to the right or the left in such a region, but not both.

As argued above $\exp(-ipx)\exp(ipx)=1$. If applied to a $\exp(ipave)$ and $\exp(-ipave)$, however, one has: $(\exp(ipave) + \exp(-ipave))^* (\exp(ipave) + \exp(-ipave))$ which is not 1 i.e. there is a real probability density. Similarly one may create averages of $pave$ and $pave pave$ i.e.

$$\langle pave \rangle = (\exp(ipave) + \exp(-ipave))^* (pave \exp(ipave) - pave \exp(-ipave)) = -2i pave \sin(2pave x)$$

$$\langle pave pave \rangle = 2 pave pave \cos(2pave x) \quad ((3))$$

Thus the first distribution form, $\cos(px)$, from $\exp(ipx)$ is linked with even powers of $pave$ which seem to represent state quantities like kinetic energy while $\sin(pave x)$ the dynamic second part is linked to odd powers of $pave$ i.e. a state quantity multiplied by $pave$ which is energy flow. Interestingly, force $= -dV/dx$ seems to be linked to an odd power of p (i.e. p to the power 3) if one takes the derivative d/dx of the time-independent Schrodinger equation.

The Bound State Schrodinger Equation

For a bound state one has a potential $V(x)$. As argued above for a particle in a box with infinite potential walls, due to the uncertainty of the particle position due to the wavelength one may not exclude $-p$. Thus p and $-p$ are taken together with their dynamic probabilities. If a $V(x)$ is present one may imagine many sets of p and $-p$ i.e. a distribution:

$$W(x) = \text{Sum over } p \ a(p) \exp(ipx) \quad ((4))$$

Why should interference occur in the first place? The potential $V(x)$ delivers impulse hits changing p to p_1 etc, but one does not know exactly where p or p_1 are i.e. where the particle is.

One has distributions for each and each distribution is changing hence $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$ and $\exp(ip_1 x)$ and $\exp(-ip_1 x)$ appear. Thus there is an overall interference scenario given by ((4))

((4)) seems a bit convoluted when compared to classical mechanics for which changes occur from one dx to another. An immediate question arises as to how one may make ((4)) compatible with the classical concept of conservation of energy given that one decides to use a classical $V(x)$ potential. It seems the only way is to use the average $pp/2m$ - average density approach. It has been seen above that $W^*(x)W(x)$ yields a spatial density and average kinetic energy $W^*(x)(-1/2m d/dx d/dx) W(x)$. Thus using averages:

$$W^*(x) (-1/2m d/dx d/dx) W(x) + V(x) W^*(x)W(x) = E_n W^*(x)W(x) \quad ((5))$$

Pulling out $W^*(x)$ yields the time-independent Schrodinger equation which has real orthonormal solutions and discrete E_n .

High Energy Limit

We wish to focus in particular on the high n limit. As noted the classical density is $C_1 dx/v(x)$. $W_n^*(x)W_n(x)$ for high n has an envelope touching the peaks which approximates this value, but it also has periodic quantum oscillations. If one considers $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$ for a p very large then we question allowing $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$ to interfere. The form $\exp(ipx)$ we argue still holds because there is still a resolution issue linked to lengths proportional to $1/p$ and dynamic behaviour. We argued above that $\exp(ipx)$ should really hold in the classical limit indicating that quantum effects are still present in macroscopic systems. What we question here is interference especially of $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$ when p is very large. In addition, the time-independent Schrodinger equation may be an approximation for high n . For the ground state the large uncertainty in position due to wavelengths comparable to the system size force on to consider p and $-p$ together, but this issue does not exist for high n .

As a result we suggest the following approximation for high n . One may consider a dx region which holds one or several $1/p$ wavelength segments and simply have p change from one to the next using $p=m v(x)$ where $v(x)$ is the classical velocity. In such a scenario forward and backwards motion is separated and quantum interference is gone, but $\exp(ipx)$ still remains i.e. quantum resolution and dynamics are still present. This seems to be similar to the ideas of decoherence at large n (1).

Conclusion

In conclusion we suggest that the free particle quantum wavefunction $\exp(ipx)$ which follows from a classical action with x and t treated as independent may be of a classical nature in the following sense. Classical mechanics breaks one dimensional space into small dx units. $v(x)$ the velocity is considered to be constant within such a unit to first order thus $dx= v(x) dt$. Spatial density is defined as $C_1 dt = C_1 dx/v(x)$. If a particle is resolved to be within a dx unit its distribution should drop to zero at the endpoints of dx . This contradicts $C_1 dx/v(x)$ being a

constant. Thus in Part I, we argued that a distribution dropping to zero within dx units is part of a dynamic probability. A shifted distribution, also showing the same resolution is needed (added in a second dimension or with i) to demonstrate dynamics. The overall modulus should be 1 everywhere for constant motion. This leads again to the idea of $\exp(ipx)$ which already follows from a classical action. Thus we argue that $\exp(ipx)$ is closely linked to the classical world, it just is not being resolved i.e. $1/p$ wavelength type units are small compared with dx .

In the quantum world, $\exp(ipx)$ also holds, but there is much interference. Why is there interference? We argue that it is because $1/p$'s are of the order of the length of the system. Thus one must bring in $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$ together as well as other $\exp(ip_1 x)$'s and $\exp(-ip_1 x)$'s. This leads to overall interference and a set of crests and troughs. The time independent Schrodinger equation is a statement of conserved average energy in particular one considers the average kinetic energy as $-\frac{1}{2m} W^*(x) \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W(x)$ where $W(x) = \text{Sum over } p \text{ } a(p)\exp(ipx)$. This average makes use of interference.

For high n , it is not clear that interference plays a role as the wavelength of $1/p$ is very small. It seems there is no reason to include $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$ together. One may simply consider a $p(x)$ value within each dx . $\exp(ipx)$, however, still holds in the classical limit (because it may be obtained from classical physical ideas). Thus there is still some quantum behaviour at the macroscopic level we argue, just not the interference which is prevalent for low energy levels. Furthermore the time-independent Schrodinger equation may become an approximation for high energies. Two slit interference, however, may still occur because it is based on $\exp(ipx)$. We argue that these ideas may be linked to decoherence theories (1).

References

1. Zurek, W. H. Decoherence, Einselection and the Quantum Origins of the Classical (Los Alamos 2003) <https://arxiv.org/pdf/quant-ph/0105127.pdf>